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Engaging Engineering students into active collaborative learning

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INTRODUCTION

Nowadays a number of transversal competencies are expected to be achieved in addition to the specific competencies of each subject. In order to facilitate this goal, instructors in general should transform themselves and their classes from a direct teaching/learning dichotomy into a kind of coaching and blended teaching/learning.

After having developed a methodology involving many facets of blended learning which include flipped learning as an integral part of tackling theoretical principles, problem solving and computing sessions, we have gone into a further blended methodology that facilitates and requires punctual collaborative learning while getting ready for relevant moments of evaluation in a first year Mathematics subject of Aerospace Engineering at Technical University of Valencia (Valencia, Spain).

The procedure developed consists in adding a task of selected exercises that the students are required to bring solved so that they may use them while solving some appropriate multiple choice tests based on the exercises of the task and including some slight difference. Students answer to this test individually and immediately after within small groups.

In this paper we present the activities undertaken which in a natural way help to develop some transversal competencies such as critical analysis, scientific and technological communication and collaborative working in addition to the pursued specific mathematical competencies. We analyse the students' opinion about the collaborative learning applied in the subject and discuss the results and questionnaire used to get the students' opinion.

1 THE SETTING

1.1 The subject

Mathematics I is a compulsory and annual subject with 12 ECTS of which 75% correspond to Theory / Problems (TP) sessions and the remaining 25% to lab practices (LP), taught in the first year of Aerospace Engineering [3] at the School of Design Engineering (ETSID) of the Technical University of Valencia (UPV).

One of the main competences that students must acquire in the Aerospace Engineering degree is the resolution of mathematical problems through the subjects of the Department of Applied Mathematics, Mathematics I being the first of them.

There are two different groups: one is High Academic Performance (ARA) which involves 51 students, with teaching in English, and the other one which involves 77 students, called NARA, with teaching in Spanish. Both groups follow the same methodology in Mathematics classes and there is no difference in topics, assignments or exams, just the language as means of instruction and communication.

The professors of the subject encourage collaborative learning among students throughout a number of activities related to the specific competencies that they must acquire within the subject. This collaborative learning facilitates the continuous assessment of students and allows them to customize their improvement needs in particular cases.

The methodology is extended to other mathematics subjects of this degree and in general to all those related to Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM).

1.2 About collaborative learning

Collaborative learning is given when two or more people learn something together, benefiting from the knowledge, resources and skills of the other group members, while evaluating their ideas, resources and skills, [4-6].

Therefore, in collaborative learning, students are involved in a common task in which each individual is both teacher and student, developing the critical capacity to discuss or refute ideas and at the same time offer knowledge. We can say that the objective of this methodology is to seek understanding, meaning or solutions or to create an artefact or product through group collaboration.

Collaborative learning provides a different approach to the traditional teacher-student relationship in the classroom, not without controversy since some authors question the possible benefits that can be obtained [7-8]. The activities that can be included in collaborative learning are wide, and include among others, collaborative writing, group projects, joint problem solving, debates, study teams and other activities. Also the possibility of planning the activities for the realization inside the classroom or outside it, or the high adaptability in difficulty and length must be added [9-12]. In some approaches, this collaboration arises in an unplanned way and can be closely related to cooperative learning. Some faculty members design work in small groups around specific sequential steps or tightly structured tasks. In some collaborative learning environments, the student's task is to create a clearly delineated product; in others, the task is not really to produce a product, but to participate in a process, an exercise in response to the work of others or to get involved in the analysis and creation of meaning.

1.3 Our approach to collaborative learning

Our approach is developed within a process of continuous evaluation, based on a significant increase in the number of control points of the evaluation of the subject, and is framed as part of the process of achievement of specific and transversal competences. The traditional form of evaluation is through individual tests, but in the process, collaborative and even cooperative learning can take place.

Collaborative learning has been designed taking into account that the fundamental objective is to maintain or increase the acquisition of specific competences in Mathematics, while developing the analytical and critical spirit of the students and their specific communicative competences in Mathematics.

Collaborative learning is facilitated by the realization of classroom activities that are the final phase of preparation of the subject before traditional individual exams are conducted. Little weight in the evaluation is given to these activities prior to the exam (15% of the general theoretical assessment / problem solving) by evaluating individual and group tests based on assignments that are made public 2 weeks before the traditional exam.

Fig. 1. Students doing the individual test

Fig. 2. Students doing the group test

The assignments are designed with different levels of difficulty and to be worked initially individually. The tasks can be consulted during the individual test. We can see the students doing this test in Fig. 1. Once the individual test is finished, the students are required to collaborate within a group of up to four students to analyze the options they consider valid and obtain their opinion on the correct answer, as can be seen in Fig. 2. During this test, the students cannot consult their individual assignment in order to encourage a critical analysis of the answers of their classmates and their own answers, and avoid the simple comparison of results. That is, we encourage the development of other key competences, such as oral communication skills related to scientific and technological language, leadership, critical thinking and the ability to adapt to other environments that face other opinions.

During the group test, the students, unable to use the results of their individual tests, must defend their opinion simply by using their oral communication skills and their mathematical competencies, without the support of solved exercises that can simplify their point of view by pointing out a result.

In this way, the possible deficiencies and strengths of their specific mathematical competences arise while they have to use their communication skills to ask or defend their selected answers when speaking with their peers. This facilitates collaborative learning through lively discussions among students immediately after working introspectively each of them in the proposed exercises.

This methodology implies a greater involvement of the student in the achievement of the objectives of the course given that he can obtain continuous feedback of his level of achievement, while receiving help to direct his efforts in those specific areas of the subject that require more practice or deeper learning.

Increasing the number of control points implies the increase of the immediate perception of the results and of their level of acquisition of specific competences, motivating the student and channelling their efforts towards a homogenization in their levels of acquisition of the subject's competences. The collaborative discussion of their results among them facilitates the development of transversal competences such as critical analysis, problem solving and communication, among others.

Finally, the early detection of students with more difficulties makes it possible to complement their activity to achieve the final objectives of the subject.

Clearly, the objective is not only an increase in the number of control points of the continuous assessment, but facilitating and encouraging the collaboration among the students so that they increase and develop both the specific competences of the subject and others of transversal type.

The specific objectives of our methodology can be summarized in:

- Facilitate collaboration among students as a group while increasing their evaluable control points. This should not imply saturation with more activities, but adapt them to collaborative learning.
- Integrate collaboration as a self-assessment and diagnostic procedure
- Encourage the active participation of students in the design of their curricular adaptation.

2 RESULTS AND FEEDBACK

The results and the rates of return are good since the study group obtained very high cut marks, and less than 10% of the students have problems to follow the course. Despite this low rate, it is necessary to have procedures capable of detecting situations in which students have problems of follow-up, and also offer solutions to correct possible deficits that arise.

By comparing the notes obtained by the students in the individual exam and the group exam (subtracting the group note from the individual one), we can draw several conclusions. On the one hand, the difference is always positive, which means that to date, the group qualifications are always higher than the individual ones, which reinforces the hypothesis that the group activity improves the students' performance and that the interaction between them can be considered a positive factor in their learning process.

On the other hand, if in each group we calculate the difference between the individual grade and the group grades squared and add these values, and divide by 400 (which would be the maximum possible value) we obtain the group efficiency. The values obtained in the course are shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Group efficiency calculated from individual and group grades.

These data may help to carry out a gamification process (rewarding the most efficient teams according to the grades obtained) or even to reinforce transversal competences.

In order to obtain the opinion of the students of the methodology followed, the opinion of the students about this work system was requested. Specifically, the students were asked to answer some questions. The declarations and the distribution of the answers are shown in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1. Concerning the **individual test** I think that:

	ARA	NARA	Total
I get aware of my level of competence and they influence my learning process	10 (20%)	19 (25%)	29 (23%)
I do not change my perception of what I know, and they influence little on my learning process	19 (37%)	25 (32%)	44 (34%)
I would rather not do them as they do not influence on my learning process	22 (43%)	33 (43%)	55 (43%)
	51	77	128

Table 2. Concerning the **group tests** I think that:

	ARA	NARA	Global
I get aware of my level of competence	6 (12%)	4 (5%)	10 (8%)
I usually learn something	21 (41%)	32 (42%)	53 (41%)
They do not influence on my learning process	9 (18%)	20 (26%)	29 (23%)
They add little value but I like doing them	6 (12%)	12 (16%)	18 (14%)
They are a loss of time	9 (18%)	9 (12%)	18 (14%)
	51	77	128

The tests that are carried out during the individual and group part are of multiple choice and require a lot of attention and reasoning to distinguish the correct answer from the four possible answers provided for each question.

In general, we can notice that the students have a positive perspective of the collaborative part of each exam and a negative one of the individual part. This can be understood if we bear in mind that the first part is closely related to the previous task and this involves hard work.

When the collaborative part comes into play, interaction with peers is fun and helps them clarify and correct ideas, and have a positive appreciation. Apparently, they are not fully aware that the whole environment helps them achieve mathematical competencies while practicing

with others. The final stage of collaboration makes sense in our environment once the individual performance has taken place in the first instance.

Maybe they would like to omit the individual part, but the information they would get from the experience would not be the same. In order to improve the perception of students in the individual test, instructors should make them aware of the relevance of this internal vision that allows for further collaborative work based on their personal introspective work.

3 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Due to their situation in the first stages of their studies, we have considered important that while students achieve specific mathematical competences, they do so by facilitating the development of other transversal competences such as scientific communication, collaboration with partners, thinking critical, all of which prepares them for their continuing education and lifelong learning.

The collaborative work developed in class facilitates a deeper achievement of specific competences. Students should be aware that this collaborative work is carried out once they have achieved some mathematical competence and a personal critical thinking that allows them to communicate and discuss with their peers. The relevance is not in the test itself or in the collaborative work, but in the mathematical and key competences developed and achieved in the process that should become evident in the mathematical competences that they will demonstrate to have achieved in the subsequent individual exams.

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